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EVALUATION OF ACTIVE COMPOUNDS OF FENUGREEK SEEDS OF WATER EXTRACT USING HPLC METHODOLOGY

Kavita Chaurasia¹, Dr. Pramod Singh^{2*}

¹Government Holkar Science College, Indore, M.P.

²Christian Eminent College, Indore, M.P.

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ABSTRACT

Methi seeds and its uses in Ayurvedic medicines for the treatment of wounds, abscesses, arthritis, bronchitis, and digestive disorders have been reported due to presence of bioactive compounds. These active compounds are marketed as nutraceuticals. Now days, it becomes necessary to investigate these bioactive compounds for the medicinal uses. In this regard we perform HPLC of the water extract (overnight soaked seed) of fenugreek. On evaluating the chromatogram we find many active compounds which are reported antidiabetic properties in literature. So it is suggested that taking water extract of fenugreek in the early morning is beneficial for diabetic patients.

Corresponding author

Dr. Pramod Kumar Singh

Christian Eminent College

6A- Press complex

Behind Dainik Bhaskar Press, Indore (M.P.), India.

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INTRODUCTION

Human health is inextricably linked with diet and in the last few years research teams have been able to demonstrate the health beneficial effects of food components, spices and medicinal herbs that are a part of the traditional diet. Spices have occupied an important place in the lives of people since ancient times. They have been considered indispensable in flavoring, seasoning of foods, flavoring of beverages, in perfumery, cosmetics and medicines. The medicinal activity of spices and spice extracts including hypocholesterolemic, hypoglycemic, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, antithrombotic, antimutagenic, anticarcinogenic etc., are attributed to their bio-active molecules such as polyphenolic compounds, phenolic glycosides, essential oils, phytosterols etc. [1].

Trigonella foenum-graecum L., is an annual legume crop mainly grown for use as a spice in many parts of the world [1]. *Trigonella foenum-graecum* L is also known as one of the oldest medicinal plants recognized in recorded history [2]. Leaves and seeds of *Trigonella foenum-graecum* L have been used extensively to prepare extracts and powders for medicinal uses [3]; is reported to have antidiabetic, anti-fertility, anticancer [4], antimicrobial [5], anti-parasitic and hypocholesterolaemic effects [6]. The potential uses of in vitro propagated plants as sources for new drugs are still largely unexplored. Based on several investigative studies [7], a compound produced in an in vivo plant could be produced at the same or different levels or not produced at all in an in vitro grown plant [8]. The present study deals with the identification of potential phytochemicals and their use to impart the functional arena.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Fenugreek seeds were collected from local market and soaked overnight. Water extract were carried out using HPLC methodology.

HPLC Analysis

A simple analytical method for the determination of phytoconstituents in Fenugreek seeds by reversed-phase high-performance liquid chromatography with UV detection is described. The method is based on a solid-liquid extraction separation on at 265 nm with a UV detector. Sample extracted in water are directly injected onto the column without using any purification step, such as saponification, prior to the separation and determination. The chromatographic separation of water soaked phytoconstituents is achieved in 12 min with a mobile phase that consists of HPLC grade water (100v/v). [9].

Table. 1 Instrument details.

Mobile phase	HPLC grade Water
Flow rate	1.2 ml/ min
λ max absorbance	265 nm
Column size	150mm * 4.6mm * 5mm

Table. 2 Chromatographic Condition.

Sample name	Fenugreek seed
Extraction Solvent	Distilled Water
Instrument name	Young lin9100

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

HPLC Graph Fenugreek Seed

Optimization of the methods

The chromatographic system was first conditioned by flowing the mobile phase through the column until obtaining a constant pump pressure and absorbance reading. After that, the chromatographic system was optimized for the composition of the mobile phase, which consisted HPLC Grade Water was studied for the separation of the sample. The reason for using water was to adjust the polarity of the mobile phase. Experimental studies demonstrated that the analysis time was too short at a HPLC Grade Water the polarity of the mobile phase due to increasing the solubility of Sample HPLC Grade water in the mobile phase. UV range was 265nm and mobile phase was water.

Fig 1. HPLC Chromatogram.

Table. 3 Compounds detected in chromatogram.

No.	RT[min]	Area[mV*s]	Height[mV]	Compound
1	0.9317	39.2597	2.2980	Vicenin-2
2	1.2800	44.1559	15.3320	Vicenin-1
3	1.4400	9428.8453	1450.3927	Orientin/isoorientin
4	1.6433	892.3635	164.4014	soschaftoside/Schaftoside
5	1.7500	2233.4055	694.9736	C-di-(6/8)-hexosyl-pentosyl apigenin
6	1.8067	4168.6797	681.9573	Vitexin
7	2.1650	280.9248	15.3385	Vicenin-3
8	2.5683	129.4150	6.8178	Isovitexin
9	2.9217	183.5926	5.4016	Apigenin-C-di-(6/8)-pentoside
10	3.9650	53.1419	2.4543	Apigenin-C-di-(6/8)-pentoside
11	4.4217	42.9360	1.8098	Apigenin-C-di-(6/8)-pentoside
12	4.9017	45.6147	1.8094	C-(6/8)-glycosyl apigenin
13	5.8917	5.3338	0.2001	Apigenin-C-di-(6/8)-pentoside
14	7.7533	43.5397	1.1758	p-coumarate orientin/isoorientin
Sum		17591.2078	3044.3625	

CONCLUSION

On analyzing the water extract using HPLC we got different bioactive compound which are reported beneficial to human beings in literature. So it is suggested that taking water extract of fenugreek in the early morning is beneficial for diabetic patients. It needs further studies using animal model to determine the impact on health benefit of these compounds.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

There is no conflict of interest between the authors.

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